

Step 1: download all PDB entries by filtering for *Homo Sapiens* (resolution < 2.7 Å) from <https://www.rcsb.org/pages/general/summaries>.

File name	Description
resolu.idx	List of all PDB ID codes and data resolution values. Resolution value is -1.00 for entries determined by NMR.
source.idx	List of all PDB ID codes and source names as found in the compound records.

From this point, I will share an example with you as a visual aid. Let's take the PDB entry **1QUQ** as our example. Keep in mind that I use a loop to run the following steps for all the PDB entries from step 1.

Step 2: Convert the PDB structure to ICM object using this script in ICM. The result is shown in Figure 1.

```
n=1
while n <= Nof(a_*)
  if (Nof(a_&n & a_A)>0) then
    if (Nof(a_&n/*)<15) then
      delete a_&n
    else
      n=n+1
    endif
  endif
  n=n+1
endwhile

if (Nof(a_A/*)< 2000) then,
  errorAction=1
  convertObject a_ 1==1 yes no no yes no no ""+( 1==2 ? "water=tight ":"")+( no ? "tautomer ":"")
  errorAction=3
```

2a. To remove any peptide sequence with less than 15 amino acids.

2b. If number of amino acids is less than 2000, then convert the molecular object to ICM.

Figure 1. The ICM-converted object of 1QUQ.

Step 3: Generate the biomolecule of the ICM-converted object. To know how a protein may look in a biological environment, we use the biomolecule generator algorithm in the ICM package. The downside to this method is that not all the PDB entries have biological unit information. The result is shown in Figure 2.

```
if (Nof(a_*.*)>1) then,  
  delete a_1.  
  as_graph=a_1.  
  makeBioMT Obj(as_graph) [1] no
```

To generate only one biomolecule of the selected object, which is highlighted as green below.


```
1quq_1B1 [2] ICM; 2.5Å; protein (replication prot  
a 121 A 2 sites RFA2_HUMAN  
b 114 A 2 sites RFA3_HUMAN  
c 119 A 2 sites RFA2_HUMAN  
d 115 A 2 sites RFA3_HUMAN
```

Figure 2. Biomolecule 1QUQ_1B1.

Step 4: Run icmPocketFinder on the biomolecule using default settings. Make sure to delete the other objects and only keep the biomolecule in your ICM working environment. You can see the script below.

```
if (Nof(a_*.>1) > 1) delete a_1.  
  
as_graph=a_1.  
if ! no icmPocketFinder Mol(as_graph) & a_*.!H,W 4.6 no no no
```


The output of step 4 is shown in Figure 3. The output includes all the pockets predicted using the icmPocketFinder method organized in a table format, the pocket views as 3D objects. The table contains information on pocket parameters such as volume, area, hydrophobicity, and buriedness.

Figure 3. The output of icmPocketFinder. The pocket views and the POCKETS table of 1QUQ_1B1.

To see the full script, please refer to **Ligandable_Genome_script_1.icb**.